

Environmental Situational Awareness for Ground-Level NO₂ Estimation Using Sentinel-5P TROPOMI and ERA5 Reanalysis Data: A Machine Learning Approach for Napoli Province, Italy

Muhammad Zaid Qamar^{1,*}, Mohammed Ajaoud¹, Cristiano Ciccarelli¹, Massimiliano Lega¹

¹ Department of Engineering, University of Napoli 'Parthenope', Centro Direzionale, Isola C4, 80143 Napoli, NA, Italy, muhammadzaid.qamar001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, mohammed.ajaoud001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, cristiano.ciccarelli001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, massimiliano.lega@uniparthenope.it

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20407723

Abstract: This study aims to develop a robust machine learning framework for estimating ground-level nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) concentrations by integrating satellite remote sensing with meteorological reanalysis data, addressing critical needs in environmental monitoring and air quality assessment. While satellite-based column measurements provide extensive spatial coverage, their conversion to ground-level concentrations remains challenging due to complex atmospheric dynamics. This study provides the first dedicated assessment for Napoli Province, offering locally validated air quality estimation for this complex Mediterranean coastal-urban environment. A Random Forest regression model was developed using 11,325 quality-controlled observations from 16 monitoring stations. The model incorporated 12 predictor variables including TROPOMI tropospheric NO₂ column density, planetary boundary layer height, temperature, relative humidity, surface pressure, wind speed and direction, solar radiation, precipitation, elevation, and cyclical temporal features. The model achieved an R² of 0.71 and RMSE of 8.61 µg/m³ on the independent test set (n=2,832), demonstrating robust predictive capability. Ground-level NO₂ concentrations averaged 29.3 ± 16.1 µg/m³, with values ranging from 0 to 112.8 µg/m³. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of combining space-based observations with meteorological data for high-resolution air quality monitoring, providing a scalable approach for environmental situational awareness in regions with limited ground-based infrastructure.

Keywords: NO₂; Sentinel-5P; TROPOMI; Random Forest; Napoli.

1 Introduction

Air pollution represents one of the most pressing environmental and public health challenges of the 21st century. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), ambient air pollution causes approximately 4.2 million premature deaths annually worldwide, primarily through cardiovascular and respiratory diseases (WHO 2021). Among the major air pollutants, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) is of particular concern due to its direct health effects (Stafoggia et al. 2022) and its role as a precursor to tropospheric ozone and secondary particulate matter formation. Traditional ground-based air quality monitoring networks provide accurate, high-temporal-resolution measurements but are spatially limited due to high installation and maintenance costs. This spatial

limitation is particularly problematic in complex urban environments where NO₂ concentrations can vary significantly over short distances due to proximity to emission sources. Satellite remote sensing offers a complementary approach, providing spatially continuous observations of atmospheric composition at regional to global scales (Veefkind et al. 2012). Sentinel-5 Precursor (S-5P), launched under the Copernicus Programme, carries TROPOMI, which provides daily global tropospheric NO₂ column densities at high spatial resolution (3.5 × 5.5 km²), making it valuable for urban air quality studies. Since satellites measure column densities rather than surface concentrations, machine learning methods, particularly Random Forest (Breiman 2001), are widely used to estimate ground-level NO₂ by capturing complex relationships between satellite data and meteorological variables (Grzybowski et al. 2023, Shetty et al. 2024).

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study Area

The study area encompasses Napoli Province, located in the Campania region of southern Italy (approximately 40.8°N, 14.2°E). The province covers an area of approximately 1,171 km² and has a population exceeding 3 million inhabitants, making it one of the most densely populated areas in Europe. The topography is characterized by coastal plains along the Gulf of Naples, volcanic terrain associated with Mount Vesuvius, and hilly areas to the north. The Mediterranean climate features hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters, with atmospheric conditions that can promote pollution accumulation, particularly during winter anticyclonic episodes (Sannino et al. 2021). The spatial distribution of the 16 ARPAC monitoring stations used in this study is shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Ground-Based Measurements

Ground-level NO₂ concentrations were obtained from the ARPAC monitoring network, using daily mean data (µg/m³) from 16 stations (Table 1) across Napoli Province (Figure 1) representing urban traffic, urban background, and industrial environments. These measurements served as the target variable for model training and validation.

2.3 Satellite Data

Tropospheric NO₂ column density data were obtained from the Sentinel-5P TROPOMI Level 2 NO₂ product via Google Earth Engine, providing daily observations at ~13:30 local

solar time with a native spatial resolution of $3.5 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$ (resampled to $\sim 1,113 \text{ m}$ on Google Earth Engine). Only pixels with $qa_value \geq 0.75$ were retained, and tropospheric vertical column densities (mol/m^2) were extracted at each monitoring station location.

Figure 1. ARPAC Stations in Napoli Province. Red circles indicate “Urban Traffic”, green square indicate “Urban background” and yellow triangle indicate “Industrial” stations respectively.

2.4 Meteorological Data

Meteorological variables were obtained from the hourly ERA5 reanalysis dataset produced by European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (Hersbach et al. 2020), which provides hourly atmospheric data at $\sim 27.8 \text{ km}$ resolution and was aggregated to daily means for this study. Daily aggregates of boundary layer height, 2-m temperature, relative humidity, surface pressure, 10-m wind speed and direction, shortwave radiation, and precipitation were extracted, as these factors influence NO_2 chemistry, transport, and dispersion.

2.5 Data Fusion and Quality Control

All datasets were spatially and temporally aligned to construct a unified modeling dataset, with satellite and meteorological variables extracted at each station location and matched to corresponding daily ground measurements. Station elevation (from the Copernicus GLO-30 Digital Elevation Model at $\sim 30 \text{ m}$ resolution) and cyclical seasonal features (month_sin and month_cos) were included as predictors, records with missing critical variables were removed through quality control, and the final dataset comprised 11,325 observations from 16 stations, achieving a 100% retention rate after filtering.

2.6 Machine Learning Model

A Random Forest (RF) regression model was developed to estimate ground-level NO_2 concentrations, using 300 trees ($n_estimators = 300$), a maximum depth of 25, and a minimum of 5 samples per leaf. The dataset was split into training (75%, $n = 8,493$) and test (25%, $n = 2,832$) sets, and

twelve predictors—including TROPOMI NO_2 column density, meteorological variables, elevation, and cyclical month features—were used, with performance evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE).

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

The quality-controlled dataset for Napoli Province comprised 11,325 daily observations from 16 monitoring stations spanning March 2023 to October 2025. Ground-level NO_2 concentrations exhibited substantial variability, with a mean of $29.31 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, standard deviation of $16.12 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, and range from 0 to $112.84 \mu\text{g/m}^3$. The interquartile range (17.35 to $38.59 \mu\text{g/m}^3$) indicates that the majority of observations fell within moderate concentration levels, with the median ($26.89 \mu\text{g/m}^3$) exceeding the 2021 WHO annual guideline value of $10 \mu\text{g/m}^3$ by nearly threefold. TROPOMI tropospheric NO_2 column densities averaged $6.98 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol/m}^2$ with a standard deviation of $5.70 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol/m}^2$. Planetary boundary layer height ranged from 59.96 to $1,421.01 \text{ m}$ with a mean of 425.27 m , reflecting the substantial daily and seasonal variability in atmospheric mixing conditions.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of ground-level NO_2 concentrations ($\mu\text{g/m}^3$) by monitoring station in Napoli Province.

Station	Mean	SD	Min	Max	n
IT1491A	53.12	16.96	8.42	111.91	725
IT0898A	40.99	13.63	11.43	106.99	723
IT1496A	39.05	12.51	12.32	104.03	723
IT2277A	9.76	6.46	0.01	38.53	670
All stations	29.31	16.12	0.00	112.84	11,325

Note: Only selected stations shown (highest, lowest, and two intermediate). SD = standard deviation.

3.2 Model Performance

The Random Forest model demonstrated good performance in estimating ground-level NO_2 concentrations. On the training set ($n = 8,493$), the model achieved $R^2 = 0.878$, $\text{RMSE} = 5.62 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, and $\text{MAE} = 4.02 \mu\text{g/m}^3$. On the independent test set ($n = 2,832$), performance metrics were $R^2 = 0.713$, $\text{RMSE} = 8.61 \mu\text{g/m}^3$, and $\text{MAE} = 6.30 \mu\text{g/m}^3$ (Table 2).

Table 2. Random Forest model performance metrics for training and test datasets.

Dataset	n	R^2	RMSE ($\mu\text{g/m}^3$)	MAE ($\mu\text{g/m}^3$)
Training	8,493	0.878	5.62	4.02
Test	2,832	0.713	8.61	6.30

The scatter plot of observed versus predicted NO_2 concentrations for the test set (Figure 2) shows good agreement along the 1:1 line across the concentration range. The model performs well for the majority of observations in the $10\text{--}60 \mu\text{g/m}^3$ range, with some tendency toward underestimation at higher concentration

levels ($>70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). The residual distribution was approximately normal with a mean close to zero, indicating largely unbiased predictions.

Figure 2. Scatter plot of observed versus predicted NO_2 concentrations for the test dataset. The dashed red line indicates the 1:1 relationship.

The probability density functions of observed and predicted concentrations show good agreement, with the predicted distribution slightly narrower than the observed distribution, particularly in the tails.

3.3 Temporal Variability

Seasonal analysis revealed distinct patterns in NO_2 concentrations across Napoli Province (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Seasonal distribution of ground-level NO_2 concentrations. DJF = December-January-February (winter), MAM = March-April-May (spring), JJA = June-July-August (summer), SON = September-October-November (autumn).

Winter months (DJF) exhibited the highest median concentrations and widest variability. The monthly analysis shows February had the highest mean concentration ($\sim 36.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), followed by January and December ($\sim 33 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). August showed the lowest

concentrations ($\sim 24 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). This seasonal pattern reflects the combined influence of reduced atmospheric mixing during winter, increased residential heating emissions, and enhanced photochemical destruction of NO_2 during summer months. Per-season evaluation of the model on the test set (Figure 4) indicates lowest accuracy in winter ($R^2 = 0.629$, $\text{RMSE} = 10.89 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and highest in autumn ($R^2 = 0.758$, $\text{RMSE} = 7.35 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), consistent with reduced Sentinel-5P data availability due to extensive winter cloud cover.

Figure 4. Seasonal model performance on the test set ($n = 2,832$): observed versus predicted NO_2 by season, with per-season R^2 , RMSE and MAE reported on each panel.

4 Discussion

This study demonstrates that ground-level NO_2 in a complex Mediterranean urban environment can be effectively estimated using satellite observations and machine learning. The Random Forest model achieved a test R^2 of 0.713, comparable to or higher than similar studies (e.g., Spearman 0.66 in Shetty et al. 2024, $R = 0.686$ in Yagmur Aydin et al. 2025, $R^2 = 0.76$ for Milan in Cedeno Jimenez and Brovelli 2023). The MAE of $8.61 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is also consistent with previously reported values ($7.77 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Shetty et al. 2024). Station elevation emerged as the most important predictor (43.7%), exceeding satellite NO_2 column density, highlighting strong topographic control in Napoli Province. Low-elevation urban and coastal areas show higher concentrations due to traffic and industrial sources, while elevated suburban and rural sites record lower levels. This aligns with source apportionment studies identifying road transport as the dominant NO_2 source in Naples (Lino et al. 2025). Although the performance gap between training ($R^2 = 0.878$) and test ($R^2 = 0.713$) suggests some overfitting, the test results remain robust, indicating meaningful predictor-response relationships. Future work could apply regularization, k-fold cross-validation, or alternative algorithms (e.g.,

XGBoost, gradient boosting) to reduce this gap. Station IT1491A recorded the highest mean ($53.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), an urban traffic site classified as TRAFFICO by ARPAC, while IT2277A showed the lowest ($9.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), a FONDO (urban background) station. The model systematically underestimates observations exceeding $70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean bias $\approx -22 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $n = 56$ test points), consistent with the regression-to-the-mean behaviour typical of tree-based ensembles trained on imbalanced concentration distributions. The lower winter R^2 is also consistent with the seasonally compressed planetary boundary layer, which in winter traps emissions near the surface, whereas a deeper summer boundary layer favours dilution. Key limitations include the satellite overpass time ($\sim 13:30$ local solar time), which may miss morning traffic peaks, however this was a choice that was made to follow the methodology of Chan et al. (2021), who demonstrated that daily averaging of both ground measurements and meteorological parameters yields superior model performance compared to instantaneous observations during satellite overpass windows (± 1.5 h), as it reduces the disproportionate influence of transient local events, cloud-related data gaps (especially in winter), TROPOMI's spatial resolution ($3.5 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$), which may not capture fine-scale gradients, and the strong role of elevation, suggesting partial capture of station-specific characteristics. Owing to the ~ 28 km native resolution of ERA5, several stations share the same meteorological pixel, which may limit the model's ability to resolve sub-grid meteorological gradients.

5 Conclusions

This study developed a Random Forest machine learning model for estimating ground-level NO₂ concentrations in Napoli Province, Italy, by integrating Sentinel-5P TROPOMI satellite observations with ERA5 meteorological reanalysis data. The model achieved an R^2 of 0.713 and RMSE of $8.61 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ on independent test data, demonstrating robust predictive capability for this complex urban environment. Key findings include: (1) station elevation, TROPOMI NO₂ column density, and planetary boundary layer height are the most important predictors, (2) ground-level NO₂ in Napoli Province (mean $29.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) substantially exceeds WHO guidelines, (3) pronounced seasonal variability exists with winter months (particularly February) showing the highest concentrations, and (4) significant spatial heterogeneity among stations reflects the diverse emission source landscape. These results demonstrate the potential of combining satellite remote sensing with machine learning for high-resolution air quality monitoring in Mediterranean urban environments.

6 References

- Breiman, L., 2001. Random forests. *Machine Learning*, 45(1), 5–32.
- Cedeno Jimenez, J. R., Brovelli, M. A., 2023. NO₂ concentration estimation at urban ground level by integrating Sentinel 5P data and ERA5 using machine learning: The Milan (Italy) case study. *Remote Sensing*, 15(22), 5400.
- Chan, K. L., Khorsandi, E., Liu, S., Baier, F., Valks, P., 2021. Estimation of surface NO₂ concentrations over Germany from TROPOMI satellite observations using a machine learning method. *Remote Sensing*, 13, 969.
- Grzybowski, P. T., Markowicz, K. M., Musiał, J. P., 2023. Estimations of the ground-level NO₂ concentrations based on the Sentinel-5P NO₂ tropospheric column number density product. *Remote Sensing*, 15(2), 378.
- Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Hirahara, S., Horányi, A., Muñoz-Sabater, J., ... Thépaut, J. N., 2020. The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 146(730), 1999–2049.
- Lino, S., Toscano, D., Piccoli, A., Riccio, A., De Angelis, E., Pirovano, G., Agresti, V., 2025. Source apportionment of key air pollutants in Naples using a high-resolution WRF-CAMx-PSAT modeling framework. *Atmospheric Environment*, 119635.
- Sannino, A., D'Emilio, M., Castellano, P., Amoroso, S., Boselli, A., 2021. Analysis of air quality during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in Naples (Italy). *Aerosol and Air Quality Research*, 21, 200381.
- Shetty, S., Schneider, P., Stebel, K., Hamer, P. D., Kylling, A., Berntsen, T. K., 2024. Estimating surface NO₂ concentrations over Europe using Sentinel-5P TROPOMI observations and machine learning. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 312, 114321.
- Stafoggia, M., Oftedal, B., Chen, J., Rodopoulou, S., Renzi, M., Atkinson, R. W., ... Janssen, N. A., 2022. Long-term exposure to low ambient air pollution concentrations and mortality. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 6(1), e9–e18.
- Veefkind, J. P., Aben, I., McMullan, K., Förster, H., De Vries, J., Otter, G., ... Levelt, P. F., 2012. TROPOMI on the ESA Sentinel-5 Precursor: A GMES mission for global observations of atmospheric composition. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 120, 70–83.
- WHO, 2021. WHO global air quality guidelines: Particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide. World Health Organization.
- Yagmur Aydin, N., 2025. Machine Learning-Based Ground-Level NO₂ Estimation in Istanbul: A Comparative Analysis of Sentinel-5P and GEOS-CF. *Applied Sciences*, 15(20), 10997.